

Oral Presentation #22 was presented at the 3rd International Eastern Black Sea Family Medicine Congress, held in Ordu, Türkiye, on May 22–24, 2025, and is part of the proceedings titled: Proceedings of the 3rd International Eastern Black Sea Family Medicine Congress.

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: In this study, the frequency of geriatric syndromes was investigated in the increasingly growing population of geriatric individuals aged 80 years and over, who have cardiovascular disease (CVD), for whom health management is difficult and distinctive (Erol, 2016; TURKSTAT, 2021).

Materials and Methods: In this study, 305 patients were retrospectively examined in the Healthy Aging Central Unit at Rize Recep Tayyip Erdoğan University Training and Research Hospital, various tests for geriatric syndromes were evaluated. The definition of CVD included hypertension, coronary artery disease, hyperlipidemia, rhythm disturbances, heart failure and valvular heart diseases. The data were analyzed using the SPSS 26.0 program and the results were evaluated with a 95% confidence interval and a significance level of $p < 0.05$.

Results: The study was conducted on 305 patients, with 96.4% diagnosed with CVD. The mean age was 85.78 years and there was no significant age difference between patients with and without CVD ($p = 0.382$). Among the participants, 73.8% were female, with no significant gender difference observed ($p = 0.140$). The body mass index (BMI) was 30.49 kg/m² in patients with CVD and 26.54 kg/m² in those without CVD, showing a statistically significant difference ($p = 0.025$). The frailty rate was 56.8% in patients with CVD and 27.3% in those without CVD. Dependence in activities of daily living was observed in 31.8% of patients, while instrumental dependence was 45.9%. The risks of dementia, malnutrition, falls, and depression were 88.2%, 22%, 46.9%, and 71.1%, respectively, with no statistically significant differences among these parameters. However, the risk of depression was 72.4% in patients with CVD and 36.4% in those without CVD, showing a statistically significant difference ($p = 0.010$) (Table 1).

Conclusion: The study found that geriatric syndromes are common in individuals aged 80 and over and that cardiovascular diseases may be associated with certain syndromes. Frailty, dependence in daily living, malnutrition risk, and depression risk were higher in patients with CVD, with depression risk being significantly increased. These findings highlight the importance of evaluating geriatric individuals using a biopsychosocial approach and the early detection and management of geriatric syndromes.

PEER REVIEW STATEMENT

This paper has undergone a double-blind peer review process and has been approved by the scientific committee of the conference.

KEYWORDS

Very old, cardiovascular disease, geriatric syndromes

CONFLICT OF INTEREST DECLARATION

No conflict of interest in this study.

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